

Turn on Fluorescent Biosensors for Imaging Hypoxia-like Conditions in Living Cells

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ABSTRACT: We present the synthesis, photophysical properties and biological application of non-toxic 3-azo-conjugated BODIPY dyes as masked fluorescent biosensors of hypoxia-like conditions. The synthetic methodology is based on an operationally simple N=N bond-forming protocol, followed by a Suzuki coupling, that allows a direct access to simple and under-explored 3-azo-substituted BODIPY. These dyes can turn on their emission properties under both chemical and biological reductive conditions, including bacterial and human azoreductases, which trigger the azo bond cleavage, leading to fluorescent 3-amino-BODIPY. We have also developed a practical enzymatic protocol, using an immobilized bacterial azoreductase that allows the evaluation of these azo-based probes and can be used as a model for the less accessible and expensive human reductase NQO1. Quantum mechanical calculations uncover the restructuring of the topography of the S_1 potential energy surface following the reduction of the azo moiety and rationalize the fluorescent quenching event through the mapping of an unprecedented pathway. Fluorescent microscopy experiments show that these azos can be used to visualize hypoxia-like conditions within living cells.

Azobenzenes have emerged as outstanding fluorescent quenchers used for biosensing and bioimaging studies.^{1,2} Following its coupling, the azo moiety is able to extinguish the emission of several fluorophores by a non-radiative process operating under the Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET) mechanism or by a non-FRET process generally associated to the ultrafast *trans/cis* N=N bond isomerization.³ The fluorescence of these azo-based quenching dyes can be activated by chemical or biological reductants (i.e. azoreductases),⁴ that trigger the cleavage of the N=N azo moiety, releasing the fluorescent probe and allowing the easy-tracking of biological events by fluorescence microscopy.⁵ The reversibility of the first half-reduction of the azo N=N double bond is highly dependent on the oxygen in the medium. Thus, in reducing media and in the absence of oxygen, such as hypoxia-like conditions, the azo compounds can suffer an irreversible reductive breakdown of the N=N bond, releasing the fluorophore. Nagano *et al.*⁶ originally reported a non-emissive fluorophore probe based on the azo Black Hole Quencher (BHQ-3) for the detection of acute ischemic and related hypoxia diseases.^{7,8} From this seminal work, a series of azo-compounds, conjugated with other fluorophores, have been reported to inhibit different emission wavelengths and to detect different levels of hypoxia and acute ischemia.^{9,10,11} Although the use of azo-compounds as fluorescent quenchers is well-known, to the best of our knowledge, there has been no attempt to conjugate an azo moiety to a BODIPY by the C-3 position. This simple azo quencher would be useful for the development of novel sensors for hypoxia-like conditions, because reductive cleavage of the azo

bond would reestablish the outstanding emission properties of the BODIPY¹² moiety.

Herein, we report the synthesis of 3-arylo-azo-BODIPY, prepared under very mild conditions from 3,5-dichloro-BODIPY and commercially available *p*-benzoquinone bisketal (Figure 1). The initial non-emissive azo-conjugated BODIPY accommodates a chloro substituent, amenable for chemical modification, providing a handle for further functionalization and modulation of the final photophysical properties. The fluorescence is turned on under chemical or enzymatic (i.e. azoreductase) reductive conditions and also visualized in HeLa cells under hypoxia-like conditions by fluorescence imaging techniques. Quantum mechanical calculations give a novel insight into the molecular origin of the quenching event and rationalize the photophysical properties of both azo dyes and the released amino fluorophores.

□ Azo-based BODIPY dyes as turn on fluorescent bioprobes

Figure 1. Design of non-fluorescent 3-azo-BODIPY and fluorescent 3-amino-BODIPY dyes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Generally, azo-based non-emissive fluorophores are prepared by azo-coupling reactions, between *in situ* generated aryldiazonium salts and electron rich aromatic compounds, or by a Mills reaction, from nitroso derivatives and aromatic amines. In previous work, we reported the synthesis of azo derivatives based on reactions of arylhydrazines with quinone bisketals.¹³ In contrast to conventional methods known for making azo derivatives, this strategy avoids using strong acids or base reagents, and only requires catalytic amounts of cerium ammonium nitrate (CAN).^{14,15} To examine whether our methodology could be extended to the preparation of more complex heterocyclic (BODIPY) azo derivatives, we studied the reaction between hydrazine-BODIPY **1** and the commercially available bis-dimethyl acetal of p-benzoquinone **2**. To our delight, the reaction using CAN as catalyst at rt gave the desired azo derivative **3** as a non-fluorescence dark blue solid, in 83% isolated yield (Scheme 1).

Gratifyingly, the method was improved following an operationally simple two-step strategy, starting from 3,5-dichloro-BODIPY¹⁶ **4** by the sequential addition of hydrazine followed by the addition of **2** and CAN. This procedure avoided the isolation of hydrazine-**1** and decreased the amount of hydrazine required for its preparation¹⁷ (Scheme 2). Notably, the remaining 5-chloro substituent allowed to increase the chemical diversity and electronic properties accessible by a Suzuki cross-coupling reaction (Scheme 2).¹⁸

Scheme 1. Synthesis of azo-BODIPY dye **3** from **1**.

The feasibility of the cross-coupling reaction was initially studied using 5-chloro-3-arylo-BODIPY **3** and phenyl boronic acid. After screening different palladium salts and phosphine ligands,¹⁹ the best yield was obtained using Pd(OAc)₂ as catalyst, P(*o*-MeOPh)₃ as ligand, Na₂CO₃ as base in DME at reflux for 4 h,²⁰ isolating **5a** in 80% yield.

Scheme 2. One-pot synthesis of **3** and preparation of **5**.

Following these conditions, several aryl and heteroaryl groups were engaged. Condensed aromatic boronic acids, such as naphthyl, anthracenyl and phenantryl afforded the desired compounds. Electron-rich and electron-poor aryl boronic acids and heterocyclic 2-

benzothienyl and 2-thienyl derivatives were also well tolerated and gave the desired products in moderate to good yields. All these new 3-arylo-BODIPY derivatives were dark blue solids lacking fluorescence emission.

To examine the potential of azo-BODIPY **5** as fluorescent turn-on probe under reductive conditions, we initially undertook the reductive azo bond cleavage by treating **5a-i** with zinc and ammonium formate (Scheme 3). In all cases, the corresponding 3-amino-derivatives **6a-i** were successfully formed in excellent yields. A remarkable color change was observed almost immediately, from an initially dark blue solution to a fluorescent green to orange-yellow solution.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of 3-amino-BODIPY dyes **6**.

Next, we studied the photophysical properties of the 3-arylo-BODIPY **5** and 3-amino-BODIPY **6** using CH₂Cl₂ as solvent (see Tables S2 and S3). The UV spectra of representative examples (**5a,b** and **5h,i**) are shown in Figure 2 (top a). The absorption spectra of **5** corresponds to a red shifted version of the combined chromophores (BODIPY and azobenzene). In general, two absorption bands appear at 619-679 nm and in the UV region (~370-400 nm). The maximum absorption band can be shifted up to 60 nm depending on the C-5 substituent. The thienyl derivatives **5h** (λ_{abs} 679 nm) and **5i** (λ_{abs} 665 nm) displayed the most red-shifted bands. As expected, azo-BODIPY **5** showed negligible fluorescence emission (see Figure S3 for a representative emission spectra of **5i**).

A detailed analysis of the nature of the two characteristic absorption bands on the most stable *trans*-azo isomer of **5i**, based on the scrutiny of the natural transition orbitals, reveals that the electronic transitions in these systems cannot be longer ascribed either to the BODIPY or the azobenzene moiety separately, but instead both fragments are involved in the electronic excitation, see Figure 2 (top b and bottom). In particular, the first absorption at 630-700 nm, which is assigned to the S₁, corresponds to a ππ* transition localized along the BODIPY and azo aryl moieties. We ascribe the second absorption at 370-380 nm mainly to the ππ* S₃ and S₅ states, also delocalized on the BODIPY and the azobenzene moieties, although the predominant contribution in the case of S₃ and S₅ is from azobenzene fragment and the BODIPY, respectively (see Figure 2b, and Fig S6). Our calculations predict the characteristic nπ* transition of the azobenzene as dark state peaking at ca. 467 nm (S₂).

On the contrary, the 3-amino-BODIPY derivatives **6** exhibit an intense emission fluorescence in the green-red range λ_{em} 552-589 nm (see Figure 3b for representative examples, Table S3 and Fig 3d for theoretical calculations of **6i**).

Figure 2. (Top) a) Experimental absorption spectra of representative **5a,b** and **5h,i** derivatives in DCM. b) RI-ADC(2)/def2-SVP vertical excitation energies superimposed to the experimental *trans*-azo **5i** absorption spectra (red-shift applied 0.38 eV). (Bottom) Natural transition orbitals for the lowest-lying excited electronic states S_1 - S_5 contributing to the main absorption bands of **5i**.

The UV-vis spectra of **6** show a maximum absorption at 493-531 nm (Figure 2a), calculated for **6i** at λ 500 nm and assigned to $S_1(\pi\pi^*)$. This band is characteristic of the BODIPY, and is mainly localized over the pyrrole and thienyl rings (Figure 3 bottom S_1). The substitution pattern at C-5 alters the position of both the absorption (up to 60 nm shift) and emission (up to 37 nm shift) maxima. Compounds **6h** (λ_{em} 589) and **6i** (λ_{em} 585) have the most red-shifted emission. For the biological studies, the UV-vis and emission spectra of **6i** were also measured in a PBS/DMSO solution, showing values of $\lambda_{abs} = 500$ nm and λ_{em} 585 nm. The fluorescence quantum yields (Φ) of **6** varied from 0.24 to 0.95 (Table S3). The highest values were obtained for the thienyl derivatives **6h** (Φ 0.91) and **6i** (Φ 0.95 in DCM and 0.4 in DMSO/PBS). The Stokes shifts are significantly large (from 50 to 85 nm, Table S3) for a BODIPY derivative, which is very interesting to allow high-sensitivity bioimaging.²¹ All these results confirmed that the azo group situated at C-3 position of the BODIPY is acting as a strong fluorescence quencher and that the 3-amino-BODIPY **6**, obtained upon the reductive azo cleavage, successfully recover the BODIPY emission.

The photophysical properties of the 3-azo-BODIPY and the 3-amino-BODIPY derivatives can be readily explained from the topography of the excited potential energy surfaces along the coordinates relevant to the deactivation of these systems (Figure 4). Interestingly, the coupling of the azo moiety to the BODIPY dramatically modifies the landscape of the excited state potential energy surface of the fluorophore. In fact, the deep S_1 minimum characteristic of the parent BODIPY compound and its meso substituted derivatives^{22a-c} (Fig 4b), responsible for the remarkable fluorescence of these species, is replaced in the azo-BODIPY system (Figure 4a), by two very shallow minima, $S_{1,min}(\pi\pi^*)$ and $S_{1,min}(n\pi^*)$, in the same potential (accessible after irradiation at 630-700 nm). The first minimum, located in the vicinity of the Franck-Condon region

(FC), and thus very similar to the *trans* ground state isomer, presents $\pi\pi^*$ character, whilst the second of $n\pi^*$ nature, would present overstretched CNN angles (see stationary geometries in Figure S9). A quite small barrier separates both minima, ensuing the exchange of population between them. For its part, a rather planar potential connects these minima with two internal conversion funnels, CI- $S_1(\pi\pi^*)/S_0$ and CI- $S_1(n\pi^*)/S_0$, recall Figure 4, (CI = conical intersection). The CI- $S_1(\pi\pi^*)/S_0$ defining the “reactive pathway” would bifurcate the population between the *cis*- S_0 and *trans*- S_0 minima (see Figure 4a, red line path), whilst the CI- $S_1(n\pi^*)/S_0$ would exclusively return the population to the original S_0 *trans* minimum by the pathway name “unreactive” (see Figure 4a, green line path). The accessibility of the CI- $S_1(\pi\pi^*)/S_0$ and CI- $S_1(n\pi^*)/S_0$ internal conversion funnels from the S_1 minima is consistent with the absence of fluorescence experimentally observed for these systems.

Our minimum energy path calculations also predict a downhill potential energy profile from the S_3 (state predominantly accessed after 370-380 nm irradiation) to the S_1 . Specifically, decay from the S_3 would direct the population first towards the CI- $S_3(\pi\pi^*)/S_2(n\pi^*)$ crossing and then to the CI- $S_2(n\pi^*)/S_1(\pi\pi^*)$ crossing (Figure 4a, yellow line path), this latter located near the S_1 transition state connecting the $\pi\pi^*$ and $n\pi^*$ minima, TS ($\pi\pi^*-n\pi^*$). This crossing is expected to distribute population between the two $S_{1,min}(\pi\pi^*)$ and $S_{1,min}(n\pi^*)$ minima. The exclusive experimental identification of the *trans*-azo-BODIPY isomer, following irradiation of the azo-BODIPY **5i** either with red, green or UV photons, discards the potential deactivation of the system through the expected ultrafast *trans/cis* isomerization CI- $S_1(\pi\pi^*)/S_0$ funnel (Fig 4a, red line path), and points to $S_3FC \rightarrow CI-S_3/S_2 \rightarrow CI-S_2/S_1 \rightarrow [S_{1,min}(\pi\pi^*)] \rightarrow S_1$, $S_{1,min}(n\pi^*) \rightarrow CI-S_1(n\pi^*)/S_0 \rightarrow trans-S_0$ as the most probable decay mechanism for this system (Figure 4a, green line path).

Figure 3. (Top left) Experimental (a) absorption and (b) emission spectra of representative derivatives in DCM exciting (λ_{exc}) at 511 nm (**6a**), 500 nm (**6b**), 531 nm (**6h**), 525 nm (**6i**). (Top Right) c) RI-ADC(2)/def2-SVP vertical energies superimposed to the experimental c) absorption and d) emission spectra of **6i** (red-shift applied 0.14 eV). (Bottom) Natural transition orbitals for the lowest-lying excited electronic states S_1 - S_3 involved in the main absorption and emission bands.

However, in view of the similar energetics accessibility of both deactivation paths, we infer that the preference for the unreactive mechanism can be only attributed to dynamical effects, which can only be accounted for when undertaking molecular dynamics simulations. The preference, although no exclusiveness, for the non-reactive pathway has been actually observed in previous works on the simpler azobenzene system, which presents a very similar flat S_1 potential energy surface along the $n\pi^*$ and $\pi\pi^*$ coordinates.^{22d} The restoration of the characteristic fluorescent properties of BODIPY upon the reduction of the azo group is also imprinted in the potential energy surfaces of the reduced specie. As can be seen in Figure 4b, the population of the 3-amino-BODIPY **6i** excited to the S_1 would be directed towards a planar $S_{1,\text{min}}$, vertically located at 574 nm (observed λ_{em} 552-589 nm). Moreover, in this case, the

non-radiative decay of the population is hindered by an activation barrier that intercalates the minimum from the CI- $S_1(\pi\pi^*)/S_0$ conical intersection. Interestingly, whilst the CI- S_1/S_0 for the amino-BODIPY shares some structural similarity to the most stable CI computed for the parent BODIPY,^{22b,c} i.e. butterfly folding along the C8-B axis and the tilting of the group/H located at the meso position, C3-functionalization of the BODIPY core alters the energetics of the decay paths of the chromophore. In particular, the incorporation of an amino group at C3 shifts the CI- S_1/S_0 below the energy of the minimum, whilst the inaccessibility of the S_1/S_0 funnel and thus the fluorescent properties are preserved due to the existence of a barrier between the minimum and CI.

Figure 4. Potential energy landscape of (a) azo-BODIPY **5i** and (b) amino-BODIPY **6i** obtained at the RI-ADC(2)/def2-SVP level of theory.

Next, we studied the potential use of these azo-BODIPY as turn-on fluorescent biosensors of reductive media. To this aim, the enzymatic reduction of azo-BODIPY **5** was studied using two different azoreductases capable of cleaving azo bonds, using nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH) or flavin-adenine-dinucleotide (FAD) as cofactors. Specifically, we tested the bacterial *Bacillus Cereus* azoreductase (*azoRBC*) and a human NADH-quinone oxidoreductase (NQO1). The enzymatic reduction was initially tested with azo-BODIPY **5i** and the azoreductase activity was measured as a function of the decrease in the intensity of the 615 nm absorption band (absorption maxima using H₂O/EtOH 1:1). As a reference, the enzyme activities were evaluated with commercially available Methyl Red azocompound (λ_{abs} 430 nm), that is known to be cleaved by these enzymes. Bacterial *azoRBC* is a homodimeric enzyme of low molecular weight (21.5 kDa for each subunit), with optimum working conditions at pH 6-7 at 40 °C. Due to the low solubility of **5i** in aqueous enzymatic medium, the photophysical properties were measured in a 1:1 H₂O/EtOH mixture, which allowed increasing the substrate concentration 10 times (**5i** from \approx 2.5 μ M to 25 μ M) and the reduced product concentration 10 times more. However, in this solvent mixture, the bacterial *azoRBC* formed aggregates, inactivating and preventing the total reduction of the substrates (see Table S4). To avoid such inactivation, the enzyme was immobilized on a solid support (agarose gel) coated with polyethyleneimine (PEI). *AzoRBC* was immobilized (*i-azoRBC*) by an adsorption method promoted by the ionic exchange between several carboxyl groups of each enzyme molecule and several ionized amino groups of a polyethyleneimine-coated agarose support (Figure S13). Thus, the highly hydrophilic environment surrounding each enzyme molecule can also protect it from other negative effects promoted by the presence of EtOH that is necessary to solubilize substrates and products. The immobilization was complete in less than 1 h, retaining 100% of the activity, *i-azoRBC* contains 0.33 mg of enzyme per gram of catalyst (See Figure S14). The stability study comparing the free and the immobilized enzyme incubated in H₂O/EtOH (1:1) showed that *i-azoRBC* was much more stable and retained more than 90% of its activity after 50 h, whereas the free enzyme was rapidly inactivated, so it would not be feasible to do long reduction tests (see Figure S15).

The reduction process was carried out in the presence of the reducing cofactor, NADH, and monitored by the decrease of absorbance at 615 nm for **5i**. Without NADH, the absorbance remains unaltered and after the addition it decreases to 0.001 in 4 minutes (See Figure 5 and Figure S6). In the absence of enzyme, the addition of NADH to **5i** do not modify the absorbance at 615 nm. These results indicate that the release of the fluorophore must occur by an enzyme reductive cleavage pathway.

Figure 5. Time-course of the enzymatic reduction of azo-BODIPY **5i** with *i-azoRBC* and NADH (1:1 EtOH:TRIS buffer at pH 7.0). The 100% absorbance at 615 nm corresponds to 0.3 a.u.).

The activity of the immobilized enzyme against a selection of azo-BODIPY derivatives and the activity percentage (considering 100% the activity with Methyl Red) are depicted in Table 1. The enzyme *i-azoRBC* showed very good results for **5c** (125%, Table 1, entry 4) and **5f** (110%, entry 6), good for other derivatives such as 5-chloro-arylo azo BODIPY **3** (80%, entry 3) and moderate for the *ortho*-methoxy derivative **5e** (30%, entry 5).

Table 1. Enzymatic reductive cleavage of N=N azocompounds.

Enzymatic N=N reductive cleavage

azoreductases
(*i-AzoRBC* or human NQO1)

Entry	Azo	λ_{abs} (nm)	Activity ^a (%) ^b	
			<i>i-azoRBC</i>	NQO1
1	Methyl Red	430	4 (100)	2 (100)
2	5i	615	4 (100)	0.6 (30)
3	3	608	3.2 (80)	1 (50)
4	5c	610	5 (125)	3.4 (170)
5	5e	614	1.2 (30)	1 (50)
6	5f	616	4.4 (110)	0.5 (25)
7	5g	630	2 (51)	1.4 (70)

^aActivity = μ moles/min of reduced azocompound per mg of enzyme used. ^bActivity percentage considering 100% the activity with Methyl Red.

The reductive cleavage of azo-BODIPY was also tested with less accessible human enzyme NADH-quinone oxidoreductase (NQO1) and the activity compared with the immobilized *i-azoRBC* (Table 1). NQO1 is a dimeric redox enzyme (with 30,000 kDa per subunit), dependent on the FAD cofactor and present in a large number of solid tumors in all types of organisms.²³ NQO1 contains two active centers that are capable of giving up 4 electrons to reduce and break azo bonds and convert them into two amines. The reduction with the NQO1 should be carried out in a completely aqueous media, therefore the concentration of azo-BODIPY **5** was required to decrease from 25 to 2.5 μ M. Methyl Red was also taken as a reference and considered as the 100% of the activity percentage (Table 1, NQO1 column, entry 1).

Finally, we evaluated the potential use of the azo-BODIPY **5i** as turn on fluorescent biosensors in living cells. The initial toxicity studies were evaluated using the MTT assay²⁴ incubating HeLa cells for 2 h with both compounds, azo-BODIPY **5i** and the reduction product **6i**, at different concentrations (2, 5, 10 and 20 μ M). The survival rates after 24 h showed no significant toxicity at concentrations up to 20 μ M for both derivatives (Figure S17).

Live cell imaging studies were performed using **5i** in HeLa cells gradually subjected to an oxygen free atmosphere.²⁵ It has been reported that the thin cover glass placed over a cell culture plate blocks the oxygen supply to the cells beneath it, resulting in a decrease of oxygen concentration and generating anoxia or different levels of hypoxia.^{10a,b,26} Under such conditions, the azo-based fluorescent quenchers release the fluorophore upon cleavage of the

N=N double bond by the inside cell azoreductases. In our case, HeLa cells were dosed with azo-BODIPY **5i** (10 μ M) and incubated for 2 h.²⁷ Then, the cells were covered with a thin cover glass and analyzed under fluorescence microscopy at different times (0, 10, 20 and 40 min). The fluorescence imaging studies revealed a red intracellular fluorescence increase under this oxygen deprived condition (Figure 6 A, +AZO). HeLa cells under the same oxygen deprived condition but without **5i** showed no fluorescent signal (Fig 6 A, -AZO). We test the selectivity of **5i** under normoxic conditions (without the cover glass on top) and no fluorescence increase occurred (Fig 6 B).

Figure 6. Fluorescence images of HeLa cells incubated for 2 h with **5i** (+AZO) and without **5i** (-AZO) and subjected to different oxygen deprivation times (10, 20 and 40 min). (B) Confocal images of HeLa cells incubated with **5i** for 2 h under normoxia at different times. (C) Fluorescence images of HeLa cells incubated with **5i** without DPI (-DPI) and with 10 μ M DPI (+DPI) for 2 h and subjected to 40 min of oxygen deprivation time. The fluorescent images were obtained under green light excitation. The confocal images were obtained using excitation at 561 nm. Scale bar, 20 μ M.

Moreover, the inhibition of the azoreductase activity, using DPI (10 μ M, diphenyleneiodonium chloride),^{28,29} under anoxic conditions (40 min) revealed no fluorescence increase (Figure 6 C). All these results indicate that azo **5i** is being reduced by reductases and selectively differentiate between normoxic and anoxic conditions inside the HeLa cells.

In conclusion, a family of 3-arylo-azo-BODIPY dyes as novel fluorescent quenchers have been prepared. Our design allowed an easy conjugation of the BODIPY fluorophore directly to the azo moiety under very mild conditions, complementary to the usual azo-coupling reaction that requires the preparation of diazonium salts. Our approach also allowed the final tuning of the electronic properties of the BODIPY by the Suzuki cross-coupling reaction of different aryl and heteroaryl groups at C-5. The azo moiety is able to extinguish the emission of the BODIPY by a non-radiative process operating under a non-FRET mechanism. Our calculations predict that the coupling of azobenzene to the BODIPY triggers a restructuring of the topography of the S_1 potential energy surface, by substituting the deep minimum responsible for the fluorescence in

the parent BODIPY compound for two shallow minima in the azo-BODIPY. From these minima, of $\pi\pi^*$ or $n\pi^*$ character, the access of two internal conversion funnels is thermodynamically feasible, allowing the return of the population to the ground state. The absence of the *cis*-isomer during the experimental photoisomerization studies at different wavelengths, discharged the usual ultrafast *trans/cis* deactivation pathway and suggested that only the unreactive $n\pi^*$ pathway is operative. Moreover, the reduction of this azo-BODIPY allows access to 3-amino-BODIPY derivatives that possess a strong absorption in the green-red region, with large molar absorption coefficients and relatively large Stokes shifts. The amino-BODIPY species are governed by an excited state potential energy profile where non-negligible energy barriers preclude the access of the internal conversion funnels to the ground state, which translate into fluorescence emission. Moreover, an immobilized bacterial azoreductase (*i*-azoRBC) protocol has been probed as a reliable model to study the azo-reducing capacity of less accessible human reductase NQO1, present in solid tumors. These results are very promising for future biological applications, as it would allow the most suitable azo compound to be selected following a simple enzymatic activity assay. The azo bond was reductively cleaved under enzymatic conditions and also in HeLa cells lacking of oxygen, proving its potential application as turn-on fluorescent hypoxia probes.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Experimental procedures, NMR spectra, supplemental figures and Tables. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. ‡These authors contributed equally.

Notes

There are no conflicts to declare.

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